

OPTIMISM IN SURVIVAL OF THE SLUM COMMUNITIES OF KAMPUNG SRI RAHAYU, PURWOKERTO, INDONESIA

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Abstract

The urban community has several demands and problems, such as the existence of slums like Kampung Sri Rahayu, the city of Purwokerto, Indonesia, often resulting in social and economic problems in the middle of urban areas. The emergence of the problem of criminality, for example: prostitution, theft, beggars, and intoxication into something that is considered as a normal and commonplace. Poverty problems triggered by low educational and income conditions are also easy to find, of course, these problems can affect the level of individual optimism in the survival process. This study aims to find out how the level of optimism in the community who live in Kampung Sri Rahayu. This type of research is qualitative with phenomenology approach. The criteria of study participants were as follows: a) people living in Kampung Sri Rahayu, b) residents of RT 04 and RT 05, and c) aged 31 to 50 Years. In this study researchers interviewed as many as 51 subjects. Data collection using the method of assessment, interview and observation. The results of the research showed: 1) Low optimism level in the community living in Kampung Sri Rahayu with some potentials such as: graduated from elementary school to junior high school, as well as trade skills and begging habits, making the community only utilize the potential. 2) There is no willingness to leave Kampung Sri Rahayu, so the community chooses to stay and continue to live there, with the condition that so the development of social and economic problems that exist in Kampung Sri Rahayu.

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1.Introduction

The world is a unity of various differences between continents, countries, cities, tribes, people and others. These diversity and differences certainly have their own positive and negative values. Positive or negative values are the result of the behavior of each individual. Based on the experience of research on community empowerment by optimizing triplehelix relations between the government, the business world and the community, the researchers collaborated with the Office of Social and Empowerment of the Village Community of Banyumas Regency to conduct a psychosocial assessment study on the residents of Kampung Sri Rahayu, Karanglesem Village, South Purwokerto District. Characteristics of Dayak Village if viewed from the perspective of sociology seems to be more directed to the concept of slum area or slums. The general characteristics of the slum area are: First, the settlement is inhabited by dense and crowded population, due to natural population growth and high migration from the countryside. Second, the inhabitants of the village have low income or produce subsistently and live below the poverty line. Third, housing in the settlement is of low quality or included in the category of emergency housing. Fourth, low health and sanitation conditions. Fifth, the scarcity of urban services, such as PAM, MCK, electricity etc. Sixth, growth is not planned. Seventh, residents of the settlement have a rural lifestyle. Eighth, is socially

isolated from other communities. And finally, ninth, usually the settlement is located in the city center, around the terminal, station and bridge.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Optimism

According to Segestrom, 1998 (in Muharnia, 2010) optimism is a positive and realistic way of thinking in looking at a problem. Positive Thinking is trying to achieve the best from the worst. Lopez and Synder (2003) argue that optimism is a hope that exists in the individual that something will go towards goodness. The basis of optimism is how a person thinks when facing a problem (Seligman, 1995). Dietrich Bohhoeffler (in Idham, 2011) reveals that the essence is optimistic not to change the reality that has happened, but to change what hasn't happened yet.

2.2 Survival

According to Suharto (2009: 31) survival strategies in dealing with shocks and economic pressures can be carried out with various strategies. Survival strategies can be classified into 3 categories: active strategies, passive strategies and network strategies. In the process of survival, humans are described as having three kinds of strategies, including: Active Strategy, is a survival strategy that is carried out by utilizing all the potential possessed. According to Suharto (2009: 31). Then, the Passive strategy is a survival strategy that is done by minimizing family expenses as Kusnadi (2000: 8) argues. Passive strategy is a strategy where individuals try to minimize spending on money, this strategy is one of the ways for the poor to survive.

2.3 Slum Area

Diana Puspitasari from the Department of Spatial Planning and Settlements (Distarkim) of Depok City said that the definition of slums based on their characteristics is a residential environment that has experienced a decline in quality. In other words it deteriorates both physically, socio-economically and socially. And it is not possible to achieve a decent life and even tends to endanger the inhabitants.

3. Analysis

Data analysis was carried out using an interactive analysis model from Miles and Huberman (2007) consisting of three main things: (1) Data reduction, which is the process of selecting, focusing, simplifying and classifying raw data that emerged from written records in the field, which takes place continuously throughout the study. (2) Presentation of data is a compiled collection of information that gives the possibility of drawing conclusions and taking action, using SWOT analysis to identify the problem, potential, impact and results. Kampung Sri Rahayu is located in Kelurahan Karang Klesem, District of South Purwokerto. The village is inhabited by 3,640 households with a population of 15,840 people. The total population in Karang Klesem Village is 15,840 people consisting of 7,689 men and 7,790 women. Thus the composition of the population between men and women is relatively balanced. The total population of Kampung Sri Rahayu which is the third phase assessment participant is 51 people consisting of 24 men and 27 women. When looking at the composition of age, the age between 31-40 years is the most dominating.

Tabel 1. Composition of Population based on the gender

No	Age	Gender		Total	%
		Male	Female		
1	21 – 30 Years	2	1	3	5,9 %

2	31 – 40 Years	7	5	12	23,5%
3	41 – 50 Years	7	9	16	31,4%
4	51 – 60 Years	1	10	11	21,6%
5	>60 Years	7	2	9	17,6%
	Total	24	27	51	100%

One of the factors that influence the acquisition of people's welfare and income is the level of education. This is closely related to the ability of the community to be absorbed into the labor market..

Figure 2. The Optimism of Accesse

In terms of optimism, residents have optimism in themselves. This means, some of the people represented by the ASSESSION show the attitude of PESSIMISM towards the future of themselves and their existence in Kampung Sri Rahayu.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research we have conducted in the village of Sri Rahayu, most of the people have a low level of optimism or pessimism. This is due to slum environmental factors, which come from unhealthy lifestyles, lack of sensitivity to the environment. In terms of optimism, only 13 (25%) residents have optimism in themselves. This means, some of the people represented by the ASSESSION show the attitude of PESSIMISM towards the future of themselves and their existence in Kampung Sri Rahayu. To generate enthusiasm and productivity, citizens need external motivation from their environment, so that later they have optimism so that programs run by village and sub-district governments can be accepted and positively implemented for the welfare of the citizens themselves.

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